

Anti-Feminist Tendencies in Mariama Ba's *So Long a Letter*

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ABSTRACT

Several studies reveal Mariama Ba's *So Long a Letter* as a feminist novel. However, this article seeks to examine anti-feminist tendencies in Mariama Ba's novel. While indeed the novel is largely celebrated for its feminist perspective and critique of patriarchal norms in Senegalese society, it also portrays ways in which women can perpetuate and uphold these very norms that they seek to emancipate themselves from. By analyzing key characters and societal practices depicted in the novel, this article highlights how cultural expectations and internalized patriarchal values contribute to the oppression of women. The complex nature of relationship between female characters, particularly in terms of complicity in polygamy, enforcement of traditional roles, and economic exploitation, buttress the challenges faced by women in their pursuit of autonomy and equality. This study aims to reveal a subtle yet evidenced interplay of feminism and anti-feminism in Ba's narrative, contributing to broader discussions on gender and literature in African contexts.

Keywords: anti-feminism, feminism, gender roles, polygamy, patriarchal norms, women's autonomy.

INTRODUCTION

Mariama Ba (1929 - 1981) was a pioneering Senegalese writer and feminist whose literary work reflects the complex realities of womanhood in postcolonial West Africa. Best known for her epistolary novel *So Long a Letter*, Ba uses the personal voice of a widowed schoolteacher to interrogate the intersections of tradition, religion, and gender expectations in a patriarchal society.

So Long a Letter (1981) is an epistolary novel by Mariama Ba that chronicles the emotional and psychological journey of Ramatoulaye, a recently widowed Senegalese woman, as she reflects on her life through a long letter to her friend, Aissatou. Set against the backdrop of a patriarchal, postcolonial West African society, the novel explores issues of polygamy, widowhood, motherhood, and female solidarity. While indeed, the text has been celebrated as a feminist text, *So Long a Letter* also reveals subtle anti-feminist undercurrents, particularly through its portrayal of women who, knowingly or not, reinforce the very cultural and gender norms that feminism seeks to dismantle. This is revealed through the pervasive influence of traditional gender roles and cultural conservatism. Through the novel's portrayal of women who conform to, enforce, or remain silent in the face of oppressive norms, the novel raises critical questions about the role of women in perpetuating the structures that feminism seeks to pull down.

Ba's own life as an educated woman navigating a male-dominated political and literary landscape also mirrors the tensions within her work, where empowerment co-exists with complicity, and resistance is often undermined by internalized conservatism.

Feminism, as defined by Bell Hooks in her seminal work *Feminist Theory: From Margin to Center* (1984), is a movement to end sexism, sexist exploitation, and oppression.

Sexism is the belief that one sex - typically men - is inherently superior to the other, especially women. It manifests in attitudes, behaviors, and institutional practices that discriminate against people based on their gender. Sexism reinforces unequal power relations and often justifies the marginalization of women in social, political, economic, and cultural life while **sexist exploitation** refers to the ways in which societies benefit from or profit off the subordination of women. This includes the use of women's labor, emotional sacrifice, or bodies in ways that serve men's interests or uphold patriarchal norms, often without recognizing or compensating women for these contributions and **oppression** entails the systemic and institutionalized ways in which individuals or groups are kept in a subordinate position by limiting their freedom, rights, opportunities, or power. In feminist terms, oppression is the continuous, pervasive marginalization of women by patriarchal systems. It is the imposition of a system where women are forced into subjugation, restricted by gendered expectations, and made to internalize these limitations. It is often invisible because it is normalized, passed down through cultural practices, traditions, and laws.

The definition of feminism proffered by Bell Hooks goes beyond merely advocating for women's rights to challenging the broader systems that perpetuate inequality and domination regardless of gender. By framing feminism in the way she did, Hooks emphasizes that the struggle is not against men per se, but against a patriarchal system that conditions both men and women to accept hierarchical, oppressive norms. This inclusive and systemic view of feminism is especially relevant in examining the text under study, where the complicity of women in sustaining oppressive traditions reveals the deep entrenchment of patriarchal values across gender lines.

The word 'anti' generally means 'against' or 'opposed'. Thus, in a layman's term, the word **anti-feminism** would literally mean anything, stance, projection, position, take, ideology, disposition that is against, opposed to and does not support feminism.

Anti-feminism according to the Digital Encyclopedia of European History is the countermovement of thought and action that is opposed to feminism. Its thematic range is as extensive as the fields of feminism's intervention, and has evolved over time to oppose the rights gradually won by women.

Feminism has tenets developed over the years by many feminists which serve as the core principles or beliefs that underpin feminist theory and practice. They include:

- gender equality,
- social, political and economic justice
- recognition of patriarchy
- intersectionality
- women's agency and autonomy
- challenging stereotypes and norms
- solidarity and collective action
- the recognition of structural and cultural oppression and

- the rejection of violence and abuse.

From the foregoing, anything, stance, projection, position, take that is contrary to or resists feminism and its tenets as identified above is anti-feminism.

Anti-feminism can manifest in various forms, including opposition to specific feminist goals, policies, or ideologies.

Basic aspects of anti-feminism include:

- **Traditional Gender Roles**

Anti-feminism advocates for the preservation of traditional gender roles, believing that men and women have inherently different roles and responsibilities that should not be altered.

- **Cultural Conservatism**

Anti-feminism upholds conservatism, emphasizing the importance of traditional family structures and moral values. It sees feministic efforts to challenge these structures as undermining social stability

- **Critique of Feminist Methods and Goals**

Anti-feminism critiques the methods and goals of feminist movements, alleging that they are either unnecessary or harmful. Anti-feminism claims that gender equality has already been achieved or that feminist policies favor women at the expense of men.

- **Men's Rights Activism**

Anti-feminism also takes the form of advocacy for men's rights, while positing that modern feminism neglects or discriminates against men in areas such as family law, education, and employment.

- **Political and Ideological Opposition**

Anti-feminism can be part of a broader political and ideological opposition to progressive movements, often linked to conservative or right-wing politics.

For the purpose of this paper, anti-feminism will be gleaned at through the lens of the first two aspects of anti-feminism noted above- traditional gender roles and cultural conservatism to reveal how women are complicit in perpetrating sexism, sexist exploitation and oppression thereby negating the concept of feminism. This paper seeks to reveal that in spite of the fact that the text *So Long a Letter* has long been praised as a feminist text that it has subtle, but obvious anti-feminist notions embedded in it; it seeks to explore how women are their own woes in collaboration with men and the system that enables unequal gender dynamics.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study adopts the Feminist Literary Theory/Feminist Literary Criticism (henceforth Feminist Literary Criticism) as its analytical lens to explore the anti-feminist tendencies embedded in Mariama Ba's *So Long a Letter*

Feminist literary criticism is a critical approach to literature that examines the ways in which literature reflects, reinforces, or challenges the cultural and social norms surrounding gender. This theory is rooted in the feminist movement, and it seeks to analyze how gender inequality is portrayed in texts and how literary works either perpetuate or challenge patriarchal ideologies. The key premise of feminist literary criticism is the belief that literature plays a significant role in shaping societal views on gender, and thus, texts must be scrutinized for their representations of women and men, as well as their reflections on power dynamics between the sexes.

One of the central aims of feminist literary criticism is to uncover the gender biases that influence the way characters are portrayed and how narratives are structured. This involves questioning why certain themes - such as polygamy, marriage, womanhood, and family roles - are treated the way they are, and how these themes reinforce or challenge patriarchal systems.

What Feminist Literary Criticism Entails

Feminist literary criticism involves some analytical strategies such as:

- Examination of Gender Roles

It explores how literature represents traditional gender roles and how these roles are either reinforced or subverted. This includes looking at how women characters are portrayed, whether they are presented as active agents or passive subjects, and how their choices and voices are constrained by society.

- Deconstruction of Patriarchal Ideologies

It seeks to identify patriarchal values that inform the narrative and character development in literature. This includes questioning cultural norms and institutional power that uphold male dominance and women's subjugation.

- Recognition of Intersectionality

It often incorporates intersectional analysis, recognizing that women's experiences are shaped not only by gender but also by race, class, sexuality, and other forms of identity. Intersectionality, a term coined by Kimberle Crenshaw, allows critics to examine how various forms of oppression intersect and affect women in different ways.

- Exploring Women's Agency and Resistance

It examines how women in literature either resist or conform to societal expectations, as well as how they navigate oppressive structures. They are particularly concerned with women's agency - the ability of women characters to make independent choices and challenge patriarchal norms.

- Highlighting the Importance of Female Narratives

It prioritizes works that give voice to women - whether through the female authorship of a text or through female-centered narratives. This also involves examining subversive texts that challenge mainstream cultural ideals.

Indeed, many authors, researchers have termed *So Long a Letter* a feminist work. In the work of Souad T. Ali (2012), he analyzes Mariama Ba's epistolary novel *So Long A Letter* within the context of a feminist approach in Islam. Focusing primarily on Ba's critique of polygamy and her

celebration of female bonding in the face of male oppression. In *A Study of Post Colonial Feminism, with Reference to Mariama Ba's So Long A Letter* (2019), Priya aimed at discussing how the text is a spokesperson for Third World Feminism and in *Mariama Ba: An Early Intersectional Feminist* (2020), Khadidiatou sees the text *So Long A Letter* as an intersectional feminist work where women were represented at the intersection of multilayered and interlocking systemic oppressions due to their ethnicity, sexuality or economic condition. In this article however, the focus is on laying bare certain anti-feminist tendencies embedded within the text.

Using Feminist Literary Criticism as a theoretical framework, this work examines how women in the novel knowingly or unknowingly - participate in the perpetuation of their own oppression and that of others through adherence to traditional gender roles and cultural conservatism. The theory also highlights the internalized nature of oppression and the social conditioning that positions women not only as victims but sometimes as enforcers of patriarchal norms. By applying this framework, the article analyzes how the characters' actions and inactions mirror the way people erect the very societal structures feminism seeks to uproot, thereby revealing deep-seated contradictions within female solidarity and agency in postcolonial Senegalese society.

CONTEXTUAL BACKGROUND

A Brief Overview of the Senegalese Society and Gender Norms in the 1970s

❖ Postcolonial Context

Senegal gained independence from France in 1960. The post-independence period was marked by efforts to modernize and define national identity, but many French colonial structures—including patriarchal legal and educational systems—remained deeply embedded in society. There was a tension between traditional African values and Western influences, especially in urban areas like Dakar.

❖ Role of Religion

Islam is the dominant religion in Senegal, practiced by over 90% of the population. Islamic traditions and interpretations of Sharia law significantly influenced family life, marriage, and gender roles. Polygamy, for instance, was both a religious and cultural norm, and women were often expected to accept it as part of their marital reality.

❖ Patriarchal Family Structure

The society was largely patriarchal, with men holding authority over women in both the public and private spheres. Family decisions, inheritance, and property ownership were typically male-dominated. Women's roles were largely domestic—centered on motherhood, homemaking, and supporting their husbands.

❖ Polygamy and Marriage Norms

Marriage was seen as a central institution, and polygamy was socially accepted and legally permitted. A man could marry multiple women, often with the expectation that it was a sign of wealth or social status. Women, however, had little say in such arrangements, and co-wife rivalry was common, as seen in *So Long a Letter*.

❖ Education and Modernization

There was a growing movement toward women's education and modernization during the 1970s, particularly in urban centers. Educated women like Ramatoulaye in *So Long a Letter* began to question traditional norms. However, this progressive outlook often clashed with the entrenched cultural and religious expectations that still viewed women's primary value as tied to marriage and motherhood.

❖ Social Expectations of Women

Women were expected to be obedient, self-sacrificing, and loyal to their families. Even when educated or professionally successful, societal norms discouraged women from asserting independence, especially in matters of marriage, divorce, and public leadership.

Cultural and Religious Influences on Gender Roles and Women's Social Positions in 1970s Senegal

In the 1970s, Senegal's cultural traditions and Islamic religious beliefs deeply shaped the gender dynamics and societal expectations placed upon women. The convergence of these two spheres created a social framework where women's roles were largely defined in relation to men, and their worth often tied to marriage, childbearing, and domestic responsibility.

➤ Islam as a Social Framework

Senegal is predominantly Muslim, with over 90% of its population adhering to Islam, primarily through Sufi brotherhoods such as the Mouride and Tijaniyya orders. In the 1970s, Islamic principles played a central role in shaping laws and social customs, particularly those relating to:

Marriage: Polygamy was both religiously sanctioned and socially normalized. A man could marry up to four wives, provided he could treat them equally.

Divorce: Men had the unilateral right to divorce under Islamic law, often leaving women with limited recourse or support.

Inheritance: Women were entitled to inheritance, but the portions were usually half of what men received, reinforcing financial dependency.

➤ Traditional Gender Expectations

Senegalese cultural norms, rooted in pre-colonial African traditions and sustained through family and community structures, emphasized women's roles as caregivers, moral keepers, and submissive wives. Some key expectations included:

- Virginity and marital loyalty as symbols of honor.
- Respect for elders, especially older women like Aunty Nabou, who acted as enforcers of tradition.
- Female modesty and the acceptance of male authority, often equated with moral uprightness and family harmony.

➤ Female Socialization and Complicity

Women were often socialized to reinforce these norms from an early age. Older women played a crucial role in passing down cultural expectations, sometimes actively enforcing patriarchal values.

This is reflected in characters like Aunty Nabou, who orchestrates a polygamous marriage that upholds patriarchal customs.

➤ Dual Realities: Tradition vs. Modernity

By the 1970s, modern education and urbanization began to challenge these traditional roles, especially among elite or middle-class women in cities like Dakar.

➤ Women's Limited Public Participation

While Senegalese women contributed significantly to the economy (especially in agriculture and informal markets), their participation in politics and formal leadership roles was minimal. Their voices were often confined to domestic spaces, and when they did speak out it was often through personal narratives rather than public platforms.

Traditional Gender Roles and Conservatism

✓ Traditional Gender Roles

These are culturally and socially constructed expectations that prescribe how individuals should behave, based on their biological sex. In many African societies - including the Senegalese context of *So Long a Letter* - traditional gender roles often manifest as:

- Men as providers and decision-makers
- Women as homemakers, caregivers, and subordinates

These roles are passed down through generations and are often upheld by both men and women and as such are deeply internalized. This makes it hard for women to challenge the system that limits them.

✓ Cultural Conservatism

This refers to the defense or preservation of cultural traditions, values, and norms. It's resistant to change, especially when it comes to gender dynamics, marriage, family structure, and morality. In postcolonial Senegalese society, this conservatism is reinforced by:

- Religion (Islam)
- Customary law
- Patriarchal lineage systems

TEXTUAL ANALYSIS/DISCUSSION

Anti-Feminist Tendencies in *So Long a Letter*

Using the two anti-feminism manifestations of traditional gender roles and cultural conservatism, the following anti-feminist tendencies were deduced from Mariama Ba's *So Long a Letter*.

'Remember, I was your daughter's best friend. You made her my mother's rival. Remember. For five years you deprived my mother and her twelve children of their breadwinner. Remember. My mother has suffered a great deal. How can a woman sap the happiness of another? You deserve no pity. Pack up. As for Binetou, she is a victim, your victim. I feel sorry for her.' P. 71

The above quote from the text *So Long A Letter* which is Daba's words to Lady Mother-in-Law is a classical line that buttresses how women are their own woes and contribute to the oppression of their fellow women.

TRADITIONAL GENDER ROLES AND CONSERVATISM

CHARACTER PORTRAYAL OF AUNTY NABOU

Aunty Nabou in the text *So Long a Letter* is presented as a tool for perpetrating cultural and traditional gender roles that subjugate women despite her being a woman. Being a woman, one would think that she should speak against patriarchy and polygamy, but no! It is no wonder that she is described as one who lived in the past, painting a picture of a woman who is unbending and unchanging in her ways which makes her a veritable tool to be used to nurture behaviors, dispositions, values that are harmful to women. She is introduced thus:

Mawdo's mother is Aunty Nabou to us and Seynabou to others. She bore a glorious name in the Sine:Diouf. She is a descendant of Bour-Sine. She lived in the past, unaware of the changing world. She clung to old beliefs. Being strongly attached to her privileged origins, she believed firmly that blood carried with it virtues...P.29

Throughout the narrative, Aunty Nabou (being a woman) like no other embodies and enforces traditional gender roles. In her quest to have her son marry into noble bloodline and preserve traditional values, she orchestrates the marriage of her niece, young Nabou, to her son, Mawdo Ba who was already married to Aissatou; thus, playing a significant role in perpetuating patriarchal values (which feminism seeks to pull apart).

In her own words, she says '*My brother Farba has given you young Nabou to be your wife, to thank me for the worthy way in which I have brought her up. I will never get over it if you don't take her as your wife. Shame kills faster than disease.*' P. 22

That Aunty Nabou trains her niece to choose to accept and marry her son and encourages her son to marry her niece shows how women are complicit in polygamy. Polygamy exacerbates gender inequality by placing women in competitive and subordinate roles within the family structure. Thus, in the text we feel the tension and competition between Ramatoulaye and Binetou her co-wife over who stays with their husband and because Binetou is younger and supposedly more attractive, Moudou chooses her over his first wife causing abandonment for Ramatoulaye and her children.

'Attempts by friends and family to bring him back to the fold proved futile. One of the new couple's neighbours explained to me that the 'child' would go 'all a-quiver' each time Modou said my name or showed any desire to see his children. He never came again; his new found happiness gradually swallowed up his memory of us. He forgot about us.' P. 46-47

Aunty Nabou in the text *So Long a Letter* also embraces manipulation in her efforts to undermine Aissatou's (a fellow woman's) marriage to her son by going out of her way to ensure young Nabou is raised to be a submissive and dutiful wife, capable of making delicious sauces, ironing clothes, and wielding a pestle, all while being constantly reminded of her royal origin and the need for docility. This is highlighted when young Nabou is advised to attend the State School of Midwifery:

'This school is good. You receive an education there. No garlands for heads. Young, sober girls without earrings, dressed in white, which is the color of purity. The profession you will learn there is a beautiful one; you will earn your living and you will acquire grace for your entry into paradise by helping at the birth of new followers of Mohammed, the prophet.' P. 30

That she caps her instructions with mentioning the Prophet Mohammed show how she conserves culture (one that subjugates women) by projecting religion.

That Aunt Nabou's actions were explicitly designed to undermine Aissatou, the daughter of a goldsmith, whom she viewed as inferior due to her lower social status shows her prejudice which is deeply ingrained in her worldview, as shown by her assertion that a goldsmith's daughter could not have dignity or honor. By orchestrating young Nabou's marriage to Mawdo, she seeks to displace Aissatou and her children, reinforcing the idea that noble bloodlines are superior and should be preserved at all costs. In so doing, she pitches her tent against a fellow woman thereby negating the solidarity tenant of feminism; showing that women are their own woes.

While Mawdo's mother planned her revenge... P.21

'When she swore by her only son's nose, the symbol of life, she had said everything. Now, her 'only man' was moving away from her, through the fault of this cursed daughter of a goldsmith, worse than a griot woman. The griot brings happiness. But a goldsmith's daughter! ... she burns everything in her path, like the fire in a forge. So while we lived without concern, considering your marriage a problem of the past, Mawdo's mother thought day and night of a way to get her revenge on you, the goldsmith's daughter.' P. 26

'She swore that your existence, Aissatou, would never tarnish her noble descent' P. 29

'Visitors came from everywhere to honour her, thus reminding her of the truth of the law of blood. For her, they revived the exploits of the ancestor Bour-Sine, the dust of combats and the ardour of thoroughbred horses. ... And, heady with the heavy scent of burnt incense, she drew force and vigour from the ancestral ashes stirred to the eclectic sound of the koras . She summoned her brother.

'I need a child beside me,' she said, 'to fill my heart. I want this child to be both my legs and my right arm. I am growing old. I will make of this child another me. Since the marriage of my own children, the house has been empty.' She was thinking of you, working out her vengeance, but was very careful not to speak of you, of her hatred for you.

'Let your wish be fulfilled,' replied Farba Diouf. 'I have never asked you to educate any of my daughters, not wanting to tire you. Yet today's children are difficult to keep in check. Take young Nabou, your namesake. She is yours. I ask only for her bones.' P.29

'Mawdo's mother, a princess, could not recognize herself in the sons of a goldsmith's daughter. P.31

That she would insist that Mawdo marry young Nabou to avoid bringing shame upon their family shows Aunt Nabou's acceptance of polygamy which is indicative of internalized patriarchal values that prioritize family honor and male desire over women's autonomy and happiness.

CHARACTER PORTRAYAL OF RAMATOULAYE

Ramatoulaye in the novel *So Long a Letter* is presented as passive with regards to upholding certain ideas, dispositions that make for feminism thus buttressing anti-feminism. Unlike Aissatou who chooses freedom by extricating herself from a polygamous marriage that no longer served her and her sons; Ramatoulaye chooses to remain in a polygamous marriage in spite of her daughter and others begging and encouraging her to sever ties with her husband as did Aissatou (especially when the polygamy was initiated by her own husband as against the one initiated by a mother-in-law- in the case of Aissatou). By choosing to remain in a polygamous marriage although with obvious reasons, she subtly, but surely perpetrates cultural conservatism and traditional gender roles. She buttresses the notion that a woman cannot find happiness or meaning out of life outside the four-walls of a marriage institution.

My own crisis came three years after your own. But unlike in your own case, the source was not my family-in-law. The problem was rooted in Modou himself, my husband. P.32

I try to spot my faults in the failure of my marriage. I gave freely, gave more than I received. I am one of those who can realize themselves fully and bloom only when they form part of a couple. Even though I understand your stand, even though I respect the choice of liberated women, I have never conceived of happiness outside marriage P.55

Daba's anger increased as she analysed the situation: 'Break with him, mother! Send this man away. He has respected neither you nor me. Do what Auntie Aissatou did; break with him. Tell me you'll break with him. I can't see you fighting over a man with a girl my age.'

I told myself what every betrayed woman says: if Modou was milk, it was I who had had all the cream. The rest, well, nothing but water with a vague smell of milk. P. 40

Yes, I was well aware of where the right solution lay, the dignified solution. And, to my family's great surprise, unanimously disapproved of by my children, who were under Daba's influence, I chose to remain. P. 46

People talked of bewitchment. With determination, friends begged me to react: 'You are letting someone else pluck the fruits of your labour.'

To act as I was urged would have been to call myself into question. I was already reproaching myself for a weakness that had not prevented the degradation of my home. Was I to deny myself because Modou had chosen another path? No, I would not give in to the pressure. P.49

In the novel, Ramatoulaye when confronted with her husband's marriage to Binetou chose to keep quiet instead of speak up or speak out against the injustice meted to her. The marriage was done secretly as such her consent or permission was not sought and after the marriage Modou, her husband never returned to the home they both shared together because Binetou the new life would not let him. This disposition of hers to not speak up or out in the face of injustice no matter how subtle shows complicity in polygamy which erodes a woman and pitches a tent of tension between her and her fellow woman and further deepens traditional gender roles and conservatism which upholds a social framework where a woman's roles is largely defined in relation to men, and their worth often tied to marriage, childbearing, and domestic responsibility.

'I forced myself to check my inner agitation. Above all, I must not give my visitors the pleasure of relating my distress. Smile, take the matter lightly, just as they announced it. Thank them for the humane way in which they have accomplished their mission. Send thanks to Modou, 'a good father and a good husband', 'a husband become a friend'. Thank my family-in-law, the Imam, Mawdo. Smile. Give them something to drink. See them out, under the swirls of incense that they were sniffing once again. Shake their hands. How pleased they were.... P. 38-39

The painful part of Ramatolaye's marital state was that though she was not divorced, she lived as though she was because she was abandoned and made to carry out tasks that Moudou used to do; thus, although she was still married to Moudou, the marriage seemed to not exist because it no longer served her; she lived as though she was divorced showing the woes of polygamy.

I was not deceived, therefore. I no longer interested Modou, and I knew it. I was abandoned: a fluttering leaf that no hand dares to pick up, as my grandmother would have said P.52

I was surviving. In addition to my former duties, I took over Modou's as well. P.52

Waiting! But waiting for what? I was not divorced ... I was abandoned: a fluttering leaf that no hand dares to pick up, as my grandmother would have said. P. 53

CHARACTER PORTRAYAL OF JACQUELINE

Another character that was portrayed in a way that posits anti-feminism is Jacqueline. Married to Samba Diack who was Senegalese and Muslim while she was Ivorian and Protestant, she suffers health breakdown from the marital infidelities of her husband and yet she does not leave the marriage nor her husband thus perpetrating traditional gender roles and cultural conservatism that places a woman in a subordinate role. Despite the many X-rays, drugs she had to take and the many visits to the hospitals to see the doctors with regards to her declining health; there is no indication in the text that she leaves her husband even after she was told that she was not sick but going through depression; depression brought upon her by her husband's unfaithful dealings with other women. Although the text made us aware she was determined to fight the cause of her problem, the narrator never told us what steps she took to fight against the obvious source of her 'perceived ailment' instead expressions laden with mere probability are all that ends her story in the novel (*She had come a long way; had Jacqueline!*)

And I think of Jacqueline, who suffered from one. Jacqueline, the Ivorian, had disobeyed her Protestant parents and had married Samba Diack, a contemporary of Mawdo Bâ's, a doctor like him, who, on leaving the African School of Medicine and Pharmacy, was posted to Abidjan. P. 42

Jacqueline truly wanted to become Senegalese, but the mockery checked all desire in her to co-operate. People called her gnac , and she finally understood the meaning of this nickname that revolted her so. Her husband, making up for lost time, spent his time chasing slender Senegalese women, as he would say with appreciation, and did not bother to hide his adventures, respecting neither his wife nor his children. His lack of precautions brought to Jacqueline's knowledge the irrefutable proof of his misconduct: love notes, check stubs bearing the names of the payees, bills from restaurants and for hotel rooms. Jacqueline

cried; Samba Diack 'lived it up'. Jacqueline lost weight: Samba Diack was still living fast. Jacqueline complained of a disturbing lump in her chest, under her left breast; she said she had the impression that a sharp point had pierced her there and was cutting through her flesh right to her very bones. She fretted. Mawdo listened to her heart: nothing wrong there, he would say. He prescribed some tranquillizers. Eagerly, Jacqueline took the tablets, tortured by the insidious pain. The bottle empty, she noticed that the lump remained in the same place; she continued to feel the pain just as acutely as ever. P. 43

She consulted a doctor from her own country, who ordered an electrocardiogram and various blood tests. Nothing to be learned from the electric reading of the heart, nothing abnormal found in the blood. He too prescribed tranquillizers, big, effervescent tablets that could not allay poor Jacqueline's distress. P.43

Jacqueline lay prostrate in her bed. Her beautiful but neglected black hair, through which no comb had been run ever since she began consulting doctor after doctor, formed shaggy tufts on her head. When the scarf protecting it slipped out of place, it would uncover the coating of a mixture of roots that we poured on her, for we tried everything to draw this sister out of her private hell. And it was your mother, Aissatou, who went to consult the native medicine men for us and brought back safara 15 from her visits and directions for the sacrifices you quickly carried out.

Jacqueline's thoughts turned to death. She waited for it, frightened and tormented, her hand on her chest, where the tenacious, invisible lump foiled all the ruses, scoffed maliciously at all the tranquillizers P.44

One fine day, after a month of treatment (intravenous injections and tranquillizers), after a month of investigations, during which her French neighbour had returned to her country, the doctor who was head of the Neurology Department asked to see Jacqueline. She found in front of her a man whom maturity and the nobility of his job had made even more attractive, a man who had not been hardened by constant dealing with the most deplorable of miseries, that of mental alienation. With his sharp eyes, accustomed to judging, he looked into those of Jacqueline in order to discover in her soul the source of the distress disrupting her organism. In a soft, reassuring voice, which in itself was balm to this overstrung being, he explained: 'Madame Diack, I assure you that there is nothing at all wrong with your head. The X-rays have shown nothing, and neither have the blood tests. The problem is that you are depressed, that is ... not happy. You wish the conditions of life were different from what they are in reality, and this is what is torturing you. Moreover, you had your babies too soon after each other; the body loses its vital juices, which haven't had the time to be replaced. In short, there is nothing endangering your life. 'You must react, go out, give yourself a reason for living. Take courage. Slowly, you will overcome. We will give you a series of shock treatments with curare to relax you. You can leave afterwards.'

The doctor punctuated his words by nodding his head and smiling convincingly, giving Jacqueline much hope. Re-animated, she related the discussion to us and confided that she had left the interview already half-cured. She knew the heart of her illness and would fight against it. She was morally uplifted. She had come a long way, had Jacqueline! P.45

CHARACTER PORTRAYAL OF BINETOU

In the text, Binetou was propelled to marry her best friend Daba's father (Moudou) by her own mother for material wealth. This was at the time she was almost due to take her baccalaureate examination. Sitting for the baccalaureate examination and passing the said examination would have given her access to a world of independence, money making, influence; but she threw that all away to please her mother and cash out of another man's wealth. A man, married to her best friend's mother.

The fact that she did not see the ill in cashing out of her best friend's father while calling him despicable names such as 'old man, pot-belly, sugar-daddy' shows the lack of solidarity amongst

women, that is women pitching tent against each other. What was more insulting was that she, her best friend's agemate was going to 'rub shoulders' with her best friend's mother as a co-wife. A woman whose home had been a place of succor to her before she chose to play along with Ramatoulaye's husband. By choosing to marry Ramatoulaye's husband just for a home for her mother, jewelries, salary and a trip to Mecca for her mother, she becomes not just a victim but an oppressor; an enabler and enforcer of polygamy and a perpetrator of traditional gender roles and conservatism which upholds patriarchal values that feminism pitches tents against.

'Mum! Binetou is heartbroken. She is going to marry her sugar-daddy. Her mother cried so much. She begged her daughter to give her life a happy end, in a proper house, as the man has promised them. So she accepted.' P. 36

Binetou, a child the same age as my daughter Daba, promoted to the rank of my co-wife, whom I must face up to. Shy Binetou! The old man who bought her the new off-the-peg dresses to replace the old faded ones was none other than Modou. P. 39

As for Binetou, she had grown up in complete liberty in an environment where survival was of the essence. Her mother was more concerned with putting the pot on the boil than with education. Beautiful, lively, kindhearted, intelligent, Binetou had access to many of her friends' well-off families and was sharply aware of what she was sacrificing by her marriage. A victim, she wanted to be the oppressor. Exiled in the world of adults, which was not her own, she wanted her prison gilded. Demanding, she tormented. Sold, she raised her price daily. What she renounced, those things which before used to be the sap of her life and which she would bitterly enumerate, called for exorbitant compensations, which Modou exhausted himself trying to provide P. 48

CHARACTER PORTRAYAL OF FARMATA

Farmata the griot woman of the cowries is not left out when it comes to perpetrating traditional gender roles and conservatism. She lashes out at Ramatoulaye for choosing to end polygamy by refusing to marry Daouda Dieng, the doctor who had come to ask her hand in marriage upon the death of her husband, who was married himself with children. On returning from giving a letter to Daouda which Ramatoulaye had asked her to help her deliver to him, she rants:

'Bissimilai! Bissimilai! What was it you dared to write and make me messenger of? You have killed a man. His crestfallen face cried it out to me. You have rejected the messenger sent to you by God to reward you for your sufferings. God will punish you for not having followed the path towards peace. You have refused greatness! You shall live in mud. I wish you another Modou to make you shed tears of blood.

'Who do you take yourself for? At fifty, you have dared to break the wolere . You trample upon your luck: Daouda Dieng, a rich man, a deputy, a doctor, of your own age group, with just one wife. He offers you security, love, and you refuse! Many women, of Daba's age even, would wish to be in your place.

'You boast of reasons. You speak of love instead of bread. Madame wants her heart to miss a beat. Why not flowers, just like in the films?

'Bissimilai! Bissimilai! You so withered, you want to choose a husband like an eighteen-year-old girl. Life will spring a surprise on you and then, Ramatoulaye, you will bite your fingers. I don't know what Daouda has written. But there is money in the envelope. He is a true samba linguere from the olden days. May God

satisfy, gratify Daouda Dieng. My heart is with him.' Such was Farmata's tirade on her return from her mission.

She thoroughly upset me. The truth of this woman, a childhood companion through the long association of our families, could not hold good for me, even in its logic of concern...P.70

By speaking to her fellow woman the way she did, she makes herself an oppressor (of a fellow woman) thereby negating solidarity and presents herself as an enabler and enforcer of polygamy.

More so, although she was instrumental to Ramatoulaye finding out that her daughter Aissatou was pregnant for a law student Iba, she wanted Ramatoulaye to inflict pain, harm or threaten her daughter for letting go of her virginity to a student who in her eyes were not worthy of her which Ramatoulaye did not do. By taking that stance of wanting Ramatoulaye to lash out at her daughter and then going ahead to speak against Ramatoulaye's manner of raising children portrays a lack of solidarity which undermines the feminism tenet of collective action. One would have thought that she would seek to quench the fire that was brewing in Ramatoulaye's home, but she instead chose to blow the fire into flames.

Aissatou, your namesake, is three months pregnant. Farmata, the griot woman of the cowries, very cleverly led me to this discovery. Public rumour had spurred her on perhaps, or her keen powers of observation had simply served her well.

Each time she cast her cowries to cut short our discussions (we had diverging points of view on everything), she would breathe a 'Hm' of discontent. With heavy sighs, she would point out in the jumble of cowries a young pregnant girl. P. 81

And then, one evening, annoyed by my naiveté, Farmata said boldly: 'Question your daughters, Ramatoulaye. A mother must be pessimistic.'

Worried by the relentless repetition, anxious, I accepted the proposition. Moving like a gazelle with delicate limbs, she swept into Aissatou's bedroom, afraid that I would change my mind. She came out, a triumphant gleam in her eye. Aissatou followed her, in tears. Farmata sent away Ousmane, who was nestled within my boubou, locked the door and declared: 'The cowries cannot always be wrong. If they have insisted for so long, it means there is something there. Water and sand have been mixed; they have become mud. Gather up your mud. Aissatou does not deny her condition. I have saved her by exposing the matter. You guessed nothing. She did not dare confide in you. You would never have got out of this situation.' P. 82

Farmata was astonished. She expected wailing: I smiled. She wanted strong reprimands: I consoled. She wished for threats: I forgave. P. 84

She reproached me for my calm:

'You have mainly daughters. Adopt an attitude that you can keep up. You will see. If Aissatou can do "this", I wonder what your trio of smokers will do. Smother your daughter with caresses, Ramatoulaye. You will see.' P. 85

CHARACTER PORTRAYAL OF LADY MOTHER-IN-LAW

Lady Mother-in-law was very instrumental to Binetou her daughter marrying Ramatoulaye's husband Modou. She it was who persuaded her daughter to marry him because she wanted the

affluence that came with her daughter marrying a well-to-do man like Modou. By insisting and pressuring her daughter to marry Modou, she like other characters already analyzed contributes to the perpetuation of traditional gender roles. She is complicit in polygamy which subjugates a woman. By compelling her child to embrace polygamy, she stole her daughter's youth, education and promising future.

Ramatoulaye in the text reflects on the betrayal and emotional neglect she endured, highlighting how Modou's actions, supported by Lady Mother-in-Law and facilitated by societal norms, led to her marginalization. This stance of Lady Mother-in-Law does not show solidarity and thus negates that feminist tenet.

I'll tell Binetou not to give in; but her mother is a woman who wants so much to escape from mediocrity and who regrets so much her past beauty, faded in the smoke from the wood fires, that she looks enviously at everything I wear; she complains all day long.'

'What is important is Binetou herself. She must not give in.'

And then, a few days afterwards, Daba renewed the conversation, with its surprising conclusion.

'Mum! Binetou is heartbroken. She is going to marry her sugar-daddy. Her mother cried so much. She begged her daughter to give her life a happy end, in a proper house, as the man has promised them. So she accepted. P. 36

Modou, wickedly, determined to remove her from the critical and unsparing world of the young. He therefore gave in to all the conditions of the grasping Lady Mother-in-Law and even signed a paper committing himself to paying the said amount. Lady Mother-in-Law brandished the paper; for she firmly believed that the payments would continue, even after Modou's death, out of the estate. P.11

Through Lady Mother-in-Law's action as well as those of other females afore discussed, the novel portrays women as harsh critics of one another. People who enforce societal norms and patriarchal expectations. This internalized misogyny perpetuates the oppression of women and undermines feminist solidarity.

CONCLUSION

Mariama Ba's *So Long A Letter* offers a rich compendium of feminist and anti-feminist themes. While it critiques the patriarchal structures that oppress women, it also reveals how women can be complicit in perpetuating these structures. By examining the anti-feminist tendencies in the novel through the portrayal of the women in the text, this article contributes to a deeper understanding of the complexities of gender dynamics in African literature. The interplay between feminist aspirations and anti-feminist realities in Ba's work underscores the ongoing struggle for gender equality and the importance of addressing internalized patriarchal norms.

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